

Workshop: Institutional Software Templates for Aligning Best Practices in Research Software

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Summary

During the workshop, 20 participants discussed the role of software templates in adhering to best practices when developing research software, and the importance of coordinating the efforts to define what constitutes best practices for research software. Participants had a diverse range of roles: data stewards, researchers, software engineers/programmers, and library staff. Their experience with software templates was also diverse with the majority having no experience with them.

Participants engaged in three activities:

1. Identify and discuss common elements for a software template for research software.
2. Learn about the meta-template tool which was developed as part of a TDCC-NES (Thematic Digital Competence Centers for Natural and Engineering Sciences) project on sustainability of research software.
3. Discuss the need to coordinate efforts to define best practices for research software.

Outcomes

The workshop produced the following outcomes:

1. Common software template elements

Participants were split into three groups and each group discussed the elements of a template for research software. They were given a list of 14 elements to choose from, and each group had to choose 8 of the elements. The list was prepared in such a way that included well-known elements, plus a few personal choices made by the facilitators.

Original list of software template elements:

1. **Readme file**- Provides an overview of the purpose of the software, installation instructions and examples of use cases
2. **License file**- Specifies how others can use, modify, and distribute the software.
3. **Changelog file**- Records updates, new features, bug fixes across versions

4. **Contributing guidelines file**- Underlines the guidelines on how one can contribute to the project, for example coding standards.
5. **Copyright file**- Details ownership and copyright information for the software.
6. **Citation file**- Provides information on how to correctly cite the software
7. **Acknowledgments file**- Lists and recognizes individuals, institutions, organizations or funding sources that supported the project.
8. **Community file**- Describes how users can
9. **Folder for tests**- Stores all test files
10. **Folder for source code**- Stores main codebase of the software
11. **Config file**- Contains constants and user configurations settings
12. **Requirements file**- Lists all the third-party software needed for installation/ running the software.
13. **Data folder**- Includes subfolders for inputs and outputs used and produced by the software
14. **Documentation folder**- Contains detailed documentation on the design of the software.

All groups considered the following elements to be essential for the development of FAIR and high-quality software. Notice that the order of the items is not considered relevant.

- **Readme file.**
- **License file.**
- **Requirements file.**
- **Folder for tests.**
- **Folder for source code.**
- **Documentation folder.**
- **Config file.**

There were also elements that not all groups agreed on:

- **Copyright file.**
- **Citation file.**

One of the groups considered that explicitly stating the copyright information in a separate file was more important than including a citation file. This group stated that the citation information can be included in the Readme file. The other two groups considered the citation file to be more important than copyright information, because they consider copyright to be closely related or the same as licensing.

2. Meta-Template Tool

About half of the participants found the demo interesting and some of them said they will either try the tool or recommend it to someone they know.

3. Coordinating efforts to define best practices for research software

There was a general consensus that some coordination is necessary, however there was not an agreement regarding who and at what level such coordination should happen. Initially, the following three levels of coordination were discussed with the participants:

- At the **research level**- researchers should define their best practices on their own.
- At an **institutional level**- each institution/department/unit should define such best practices.
- At a **national level**- there should be a national body that dictates best practices for research software.

Other two levels of coordination were added by the participants:

- At a **funder level**- research funding organizations should define best practices because they have a strong influence in how research outputs are managed and developed.
- At a **scientific domain level**- best practices should be defined by the experts in a particular domain since what constitutes best scientific practices is highly influenced by the research domain.

Finally, several participants did not agree with any of the levels of coordination above. However, time did not allow us to discuss their points of view further.

Next Steps

All participants are invited to follow up the topic of the workshop, as follows:

- Consider using some of the software templates we have available in the documentation: <https://ss-nes.github.io/meta-template/>.
 - Link to repo for Jupyter Notebook template for data analysis: [Link](#)
 - Link to repo for R template: [Link](#)
 - Link to repo for Python template: [Link](#)
- **Get in touch** with us via email at m.g.garciaalvarez@tudelft.nl or a.momin@utwente.nl if you:
 - Have questions
 - Want to use the Meta-Template for developing a software template for your group or institution.
 - Want to get involved with promoting best practices for research software
 - Want to provide detailed feedback on any topic related to the workshop or the tool.